

Never Before.....

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Abstract: Nina Thornhill and Chris Hamlin met through the IChemE Special Interest Group in Process Measurement and Control. Nina has inspired over a period of 20 years through mentoring and support. Both Nina and Chris are Fellows of the Royal Academy of Engineering.

Keywords: IChemE, process measurement and control, integration of control and manufacturing enterprise systems.

To coin and mis-quote and much overused aphorism, never before has so much been owed to a single person (at least not in the automation world). At a personal and professional level my debt of gratitude is huge, and I know that I join with the rest of the profession and academic discipline in acknowledging Nina's unparalleled contribution.

Never before in human history has it been possible to move almost unlimited amounts of data to almost anywhere on the planet at almost zero marginal cost. The impact on the practice and art of control and automation will be profound. Many careers, including my own, are predicated on this simple concept.

Having connected through the IChemE's Process Measurement and Control Subject Group, Nina and I first collaborated around this idea almost two decades ago. In our joint paper for Control 2008 (Integration of Control, Manufacturing and Enterprise Systems) we predicted the demise of the long-established Purdue model, and proposed an alternative view, that provided a specific purpose and role for an MES, and how it relates to control and enterprise system functionality. It's a model that is still relevant and germane today (Fig.1).

Nina's commitment to building and strengthening relationships with the user and practitioner community truly sets her apart. It has been a pleasure and an honour to work with Nina to advance this collaboration, particularly in the UK. The analogy to gunboat diplomacy, epitomised by our jointly hosted event on HMS Belfast, has been apt at times, but we can be justifiably proud of the impact that we have had and the progress that has been made.

At a personal and professional level, never before has a single individual taken such a close interest in my own professional development, and acted as a coach, mentor and advocate for such a long period of time. Nina took me under her wing as a young, aspiring automation manager almost 20 years ago, and has been a point of constancy and inspiration over the years that have followed. Her unwavering belief and support has been a bell weather through times of difficulty and challenge, and her intellectual guidance and challenge a beacon to aspire to. Being accepted into the RAEng is a great and humbling honour, made all the more special by knowing that it was at Nina's instigation, and following her lead!

Business Control Hierarchy

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Risk Management

- Coping with an uncertain World
 - Prices & markets
 - Supply and demand uncertainty
 - Plant availability

Agility Management

- Responding to fluctuations and deviations
 - Alternate production and supply routes
 - Spot opportunities
 - Responsiveness & flexibility

Performance Management

- Knowing what's happening and what's possible
 - Identifying deviations (in production performance, supply/demand patterns etc)
 - Validation of planning models and assumptions
 - Driving continuous improvement

Conformance Management

- Doing what's wanted or expected
 - Staying on spec (quality control)
 - Minimising costs (constraint control)
 - Pushing appropriate limits (real-time optimisation)

Conservation Management

- Keeping the process running
 - Basic regulatory control (closed-loop)
 - Conservation of mass and energy

Control 2008, Manchester

September 3rd 2008

Figure 1: The Business Control Hierarchy, as proposed by Thornhill & Hamlin, 2008